

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B204
Date: 2nd Jun 2006
Take Off: 11:44:48
Landing: 14:41:20
Flight Time: 2h56m32

Campaign: CLAPREC / NEON
Trials Instructions:
Operating Area: Beja area, Portugal

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Martin Glew	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
6	Cloud physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	ARIES / IR Camera	Joss Kent	Met Office
8	MARSS	James Bowles	Met Office
9	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
10	CCN	Bruce Giddings	Met Office
11	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
12	Wet Neph	Andy Wilson	Met Office
13	Filters	Doug Anderson	FAAM
14	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
15	VPRACOP 1 / Filters	Fernando Carvalho	Instituto Tecnologico e Nuclear, Sacavem
16	VPRACOP 2 / Filters	Mario Reis	Instituto Tecnologico e Nuclear, Sacavem
17	CLAPREC 1 / Mission 2	Danny Rosenfeld	Hebrew University of Jersusalem
18	EUFAR Training	Piotr Drzewicki	University of Warsaw

Flight Track:

B204 Track 02-JUN-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b204
 Date: 02 June 2006
 Project: CAPEX (NEON & CLAPREC)
 Location: Portugal

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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105935		INU to Nav	0.39 kft	113	
113540		start taxi	0.40 kft	113	
114448		T/O	1.5 kft	012	
114900		Video start	7.4 kft	172	DFC IR cam
115043		JW zero	10.0 kft	168	
115104		Nevzorov zero	10.0 kft	170	
115734	121236	Profile 1	10.0 - 0.46 kft	353	50ft agl
120258		interrupt Profile 1	2.8 kft	008	
120842		recommence profile 1	2.8 kft	020	
121522		retract LBBR shutter	0.85 kft	027	500ft
121801	121833	Run 1.1	0.81 - 0.88 kft	183	500ft & start H cal
122125		end Heimann cal	1.1 kft	045	
122301	122332	Run 1.2	0.80 - 0.87 kft	006	500 ft & start cal
122656		end Heimann cal	1.3 kft	183	climbing during cal
122832	122904	Run 2.1	1.3 - 1.4 kft	165	
122832		start Heimann cal			
123152		end Heimann cal	3.4 kft	169	climbing during cal
123247	123733	Run 2.1 at 1000ft	3.4 kft	105	
123247		start Heimann cal			
123650		Run 3.1	3.4 kft	347	3000ft
123954	123730	Run 3.1	5.4 kft	321	
124324	124409	Run 4.1	5.4 - 5.5 kft	155	
124943	125018	Run 4.2	5.4 kft	350	
125535		restart H_CVI	10.4 kft	258	
130003	130039	Run 5.1	10.4 kft	166	
131002	131055	Run 5.2	10.4 kft	345	
131534	131616	Run 5.3	10.5 - 10.4 kft	167	
131801		Video	10.4 kft	166	change DFC tape
131900		Video	10.4 kft	184	change IR tape
132755	133910	Profile 2	10.0 - 0.48 kft	342	end 50ft agl
133541		change to 500ft/min	2.3 kft	012	
134451	134522	Run 6.1	0.83 - 0.90 kft	184	500ft
134451		start Heimann cal			
134807		end Heimann cal	0.97 kft	006	
134906	134938	Run 6.2	0.90 - 0.88 kft	007	500ft
135433	135503	Run 6.3	0.92 - 0.97 kft	185	500ft
140042		Video	10.0 kft	037	change IR to FFC
140621	140909	Profile 3	10.0 - 7.0 kft	313	
140936	141106	Profile 4	7.2 - 8.3 kft	313	cloud 1 base

141125	141129	Run 7	8.2 kft	325 in cloud 1
141347	141419	Profile 5	7.7 - 8.2 kft	221 cloud 2
141600	141651	Profile 6	7.4 - 8.2 kft	066 cloud 3
141640			8.0 kft	064 in cloud 3
141719	141826	Profile 7	8.2 - 8.4 kft	062 cloud 4
141733			8.4 kft	062 in cloud
141803			8.4 kft	062 out of cloud
142146	142245	Run 8	9.5 kft	250
142207			9.6 kft	258 in cloud 5
142229			9.5 kft	259 out of cloud
142501	142543	Run 9	10.1 - 10.0 kft	018
142515				in cloud 6
142527			9.9 kft	017 out of cloud
142856	143038	Run 10	10.8 - 10.2 kft	224
143005			10.2 kft	225 in cloud 7
143020			10.2 kft	225 out of cloud
143059	143143	Run 11	10.1 - 9.6 kft	198
143115			9.8 kft	196 in cloud 8
143130			9.6 kft	200 out of cloud
143245			9.6 kft	209 in cloud 9
143304			9.5 kft	206 out of cloud
143327			9.1 kft	207 in cloud 10
143347			8.8 kft	205 out of cloud
144120		Land	0.45 kft	006
144523		park posn	0.45 kft	099 38 05.13N 07 55.65W

GEOSTROPHIC WIND SCALE
IN KNOTS FOR ISOBARS AT 4 MB INTERVALS
POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION

B204 Track 02-JUN-06

SORTIE BRIEF

Flight B 204 (NEON flight during CAPEX)

2nd June 2006

Trial Objectives

1. To validate the NEON TDA using the IR camera looking at a runway.

Take off

Noon local time

Location

1. Over and nearby a runway.

Weather

1. Ideally: Totally cloud free conditions, flights around lunch time.
2. Cloud-free is preferred, but not necessary.

Instrumentation Required

IR camera, core temperature, water vapour, ARIES, Heimann, aerosol instruments (PCASP)

Special Conditions

Note that in order to keep the runway in the field of view of the IR camera all altitudes will need to be flown at exact heights above the surface and not at flight levels.

Flight Pattern (see Fig. 1)

1. Take off and transit to airfield/runway, to arrive at 10,000ft.
--- Over/nearby runway-----
2. 1st PROFILE = descent at 1,000ft/min to minimum altitude (if possible with a missed approach at the operating airfield)
3. 1st HAL (see Fig. 2) = runs at 500ft, sequence: over and along runway, loop, displaced to runway over grass/ravel path next to runway; note special needs for ARIES and Heimann
4. 20-degree approaches (see Fig. 3), i.e. straight and level runs at 1000ft, 3000ft, 5000ft, and 10,000ft (getting the runway into the field of view of the IR camera)
5. 2nd PROFILE, identical to point 2 (if possible without extra costs then include another missed approach at the operating airfield)
6. 2nd HAL

7. Transit back.
8. Landing.

Total time: about 3 hours

NEON Sortie

V/P = "fast" vertical profile
M/A = missed approach over runway
HAL = "Heimann-ARIES loop"

Fig. 1: NEON sortie Height vs. Time. It includes:

- Two vertical profiles (scientific flying), if possible ending with missed approaches
- Two "HALs" (cp. Fig. 2) to take place at 500ft height.
- Several "20-degree approaches" (cp. Fig. 3) at 1000, 3000, 5000, and 10,000ft.

HAL (Heimann-ARIES loop)

- ARIES down (max. resolution), Heimann measuring
- - - ARIES up, Heimann calibration

ARIES calibration before and after HAL

Fig. 2: "Heimann-ARIES loop" (top view).

"20-degree approach" - top view -

Flights along runway with about 20 deg angle to make sure to get runway in FoV of the IR camera ! (ala Joss' Africa Experience)

Fig. 3: "20 degree approach" instead of flying parallel to the runway to get runway in FoV of the IR cam.

Appendix A:

Height – Distance Conversion

The horizontal shift S of flight legs parallel to the runway to keep the runway in the view of the IR camera is dependent on the angle Y the camera is looking below the horizontal and the flight height H:

$$S \text{ (nautical miles)} = H \text{ (ft)} / \tan(Y) * 0.3048 * 0.54E-03$$

Assuming IR camera view = 35 degrees down the horizontal:

(Use EXCEL sheet to compute distances for other angles, <http://metresearch.net/CAESAR/>)

Ideal NEON flight levels marked with an X	Flight Height (ft)	Displacement right of runway (nautical miles)	Flight Height (km)	Displacement (km)	Displacement (statute miles)	IR camera viewing distance (km)
missed approach: X	0	0	0	0	0	0
X	500	0.118	0.152	0.218	0.135	0.12
X	1000	0.235	0.305	0.435	0.270	0.53
	2000	0.470	0.610	0.871	0.541	
X	3000	0.705	0.914	1.306	0.811	1.59
	4000	0.940	1.219	1.741	1.082	
X	5000	1.175	1.524	2.176	1.352	2.66
	6000	1.410	1.829	2.612	1.623	
	7000	1.645	2.134	3.047	1.893	
	8000	1.880	2.438	3.482	2.164	4.25
	9000	2.115	2.743	3.918	2.434	
X	10000	2.350	3.048	4.353	2.705	5.31
	12000	2.821	3.658	5.224	3.246	
(X)	14000	3.291	4.267	6.094	3.787	7.44
	27000	6.346	8.230	11.753	7.303	

Table 1: Displacement for straight and level runs to keep the runway in the FoV of the IR camera (Y=35 degrees).

Fig. 4: Displacement graph (Y=35 degrees).

Appendix B: Instructions for Instrument Operators

1. IR camera

- Get runway in FoV of the IR camera during the 20-degree approaches (cp. Fig. 3), check using spotter camera. If this fails, run must be repeated!
- Record both, IR camera and spotter camera pics.

2. Heimann

- Heimann to be working during HALs (Heimann-ARIES loops), Heimann calibration during up-view of ARIES

3. ARIES

- Record every interferogram, i.e. no co-averaging!
- During the whole flight, in particular the 20-degree approaches, look in same direction as IR cam, i.e. 55 degrees up (=35 deg below the horizontal) and to the left AND use 16cm-1 resolution

HAL (cp. Fig. 2):

- During HAL → maximum resolution!
- HAL: over runway or grass → ARIES to look down
- HAL: away from runway/grass path → ARIES to look up
- ARIES calibration before and after HALs

4. SWS

- To be switched on during HALs
- Always looking straight down, offset roll & pitch

B204 – Mission Scientist De-brief
2nd June 2006
Martin Glew

NEON validation flight during CAPEX and Aerosol Cloud Interaction (CLAPREC)
Location – Beja Airfield, Portugal, ICAO identifier LBPJ, and surrounding area

The aim of the sortie was to validate the NEON TDA using the IR camera looking at the Beja runway from various heights. Use of the Beja runway was guaranteed from 1300z but preparations were made for a possible earlier take off anytime after 11:30z. There was high pressure building over Portugal. There was no high cloud. Visibility reported by the airfield was >40 km. There was 1/8 Cu Hum to the north of the airfield.

Take off was 11:45z and the aircraft positioned for a profile to 50' over the runway from FL100, interrupted at 2800' to "dirty" the aircraft. The nephelometer showed aerosol below 7500'. The tephigram showed a well mixed boundary layer to 850mb with the temperature following the WALR above.

Next a Heimann-ARIES (HAL) loop was flown at 500'. Due to a misunderstanding between the mission scientist and the Captain this loop went runway, grass, offset which caused problems with the Heimann cal. The aircraft then made runs offset to the runway by 20 deg at 1000, 3000, 5000 and 10000 feet. Visibility was estimated at 25 miles at 3000', 15 miles at 5000' and more than 50 miles at 10000'. The IR camera captured the runway first time at 1000 and 3000 feet. It took two goes at 5000'. At 10000' the IR camera got just the end of the runway so a successful 2nd leg was flown, followed by a successful 3rd as the aircraft positioned for a profile descent over the runway. On this profile the well mixed boundary layer extended to 800 mb. A second HAL loop was run.

During this 500' work a CCN sample was taken in preparation for the CLAPREP part of the sortie. During the NEON runs there was Cu Hum to the immediate north of the runway, building to 3/8, but it never encroached over the airfield. At the end of NEON science at 135503z the aircraft turned heading 060 and climbed to FL100 to allow a change of mission scientist to Danny Rosenfeld. Shallow cumulus was found with convection from 7200' to 11100'. From 1411z to 1433z the aircraft penetrated 10 growing turrets at 8200', 7700', 7400', 8200', 9500', 10100', 10800', 10100', 9600' and 9100'. The aircraft finished science very close to the airfield and landed at 14:41:20, giving a flight time of 2h56min. With 5 instrument operators strapped in harnesses till end of science this rapid landing caused a confused rush in the aircraft gangway.

Summary

A successful flight, all NEON objectives were achieved and though the cumulus was not deep there was useful data gathered in a short time. Filter samples were collected during the straight and level parts of the NEON sortie for the VPRACOP project.

Instrument status

No problems reported

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B204**... Date **02nd 10/06** Name **M. GLEW**... Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
	NECN as part of CAPEX				
	1/8 Cu hum before take off (barely 1/8)				
	Disturb				
11:45:51	T/h				
11:56		FL100			Disturb haze layer below T/O FL100 ^{FL100} FL100 ^{FL100} to 10000
11:57:34	P1	FL100	10 ^{deg}		Neigh shows haze layer 2300m
12:02:58 12:03:58	P1				interrupt at 2800' cloud to N, none to S
12:04:42	P1 cont	2800'	9'		Flying "dirty"
12:12:06	P1 cont	500'	7°		Cu hum to N.
12:18:01	R1.1	500'	183		Along runway
12:18:33	R1.1 cont				
12:22					IR camera saw / runways, not called run.
12:23:01	R1.2	500'	006		Along runways
12:28:32	R2.1	1000'	165		IR camera captured.
12:32		3000'			vis <u>at</u> 25 miles. below cu.
12:36:50	R3.1	3000'	347		IR camera captured.
12:39		5000'			still below Cu base at
12:41		5000'			Estimate Cu base 5500'
12:42		5000'			Estimate vis 15 miles
12:43:24	R4.1	5000'	155		IR camera missed.
12:49:43	R4.2	5000'	344		IR camera captured.
13:00:03	R5.1	10000'	166		Good vis, haze/cloud below IR camera got end.
13:10:02	R5.2	10000'	343		IR camera captured.
13:15:34	R5.3	10000'	168		IR camera captured. Some haze cloud far E S+E
13:26					haze cloud to W.

30 min

13:30

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B204** Date **02/06/06** Name **M. GLEW** Page **2** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
132755	P2	10000'	342		
1334	P2				Change from DLR (to ^{800'} walk)
					Top of hanc 2800m P4GT
134451	6.1	500'	186		over Runway ALIES Nadir
134900	6.2	500'	006		offset from the Camera
135433	6.3	500'	187	135505 26.3240	Over grass, ALIES Zenith
					Changed position with Danny, the now in mission 2 - position.
140621	P3	10000'	313		
140936	P4	7000'	313		
141125	R7	7125 ^{8200'}			In cloud 1
					Clouds \approx 7200' to 10500'
141347	P5	7.7kt			Cloud 2
141600	P6	7.4kt			Cloud 3
141719	P7	8.2kt			Cloud 4
142146	R8	9.5kt			In cloud 5 14:22:07
142501	R9	10.1kt			In Cloud 6 14:25:15
142856	R10	10.8kt			In Cloud 7 14:30:05
143059	R11	10.1kt			In Cloud 8 14:31:15
143245	R11	9.6kt			In Cloud 9
143327		9.1kt			In Cloud 10
143347					Out Cloud 10, end ex.
144120		LAND			

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B204

Date : 02/06/06

Operator and contact info : Kate Turnbull katet@faam.ac.uk

Problems with Instruments

CO	None
O₃	None
NO_x	Ozonator flow low (< 0.02 lpm) at FL100 and above.
SO₂	N/A
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	N/A

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT		HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF			1	2	3	4	5	
13:40:50	13:42:00	500	T6	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	Run
		25.71	27.90	0.16	0.32	0.48	0.68	1.03	S
		23.82	27.46	407	670	877	1435	1996	D
		23.68	27.47	286	261	252	251	276	B
		22.77	22.25	2196	2203	2209	2213	2210	R
		21.68	21.17	999.4	999.4	999.2	999.5	999.5	P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
									D
									B
									R
									P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P
				1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5	S
									D
									B
									R
									P
									S
									D
									B
									R
									P

Filter Sampling Log

Flight No:

B204

Date:

2 Jun 2006

Operator:

Doug / Mario

Type of filters mounted in	Top inlet	90mm diameter types AC & PC	Bottom inlet	90mm diameter types AC & PC
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Run No	Disk #1 TOP	Disk #2 MIDDLE	Disk #3 BOTTOM	Inlet Top/ Bottom	Time On (Z)	Time Off (Z)	Flight Run	Accum Vol [I]	Comments
Filter profile	AC12	empty	empty	Top	11:58:36	12:12:40	P1	927	Late start – pump started at FL090
Filter profile	AC13	empty	empty	Bottom	11:58:36	12:12:40	P1	2140	
Filter run1	AC14	empty	empty	Top	12:14:00	12:25:	before / during R1.1/2	*see below	500' above ground level * Same filters used at 1000' agl (below) due to lack of time between levels to change them.
Filter run1	AC15	empty	empty	Bottom	12:14:00	12:25:		*see below	
Filter run 2a	AC14	empty	empty	Top	~ 12:27:30	12:30:30	before / during R2.1	671	Before and into R2.1 @ 1000' radalt R2.1 12:28:32 to 12:29:04 (1.3 - 1.4 kft) Filters changed at end of run call but run continued after change of level (see below)
Filter run 2a	AC15	empty	empty	Bottom	~ 12:27:30	12:30:30		1377	
Filter run 2b	AC16	empty	empty	Top	12:32:14	12:35:40	R2.1	181	R2.1 12:32:47 to 12:37:33 (starting at 1000ft but climbing almost immediately to 3000')
Filter run 2b	AC17	empty	empty	Bottom	12:32:14	12:35:40	R2.1	364	
Filter run 3	AC18	empty	empty	Top	12:40:31	12:50:26	R4.1/2	398	5000' above runway
Filter run 3	AC20	empty	empty	Bottom	12:40:31	12:50:26	R4.1/2	810	5000' above runway
Filter run 4	AC21	empty	empty	Top	13:28:06	13:39:10	P2	680	Descent from 10000' above runway to 250'
Filter run 4	AC22	empty	empty	Bottom	13:28:06	13:39:10	P2	936	
Filter run 5	AC23	empty	empty	Top	13:42:32	13:55:30	Before and during and after R6.1/2/3	736	Hole in filter
Filter run 5	AC24	empty	empty	Bottom	13:42:32	13:55:30		1978	
Filter run 6	P2	empty	empty	Top	14:12:44	14:23:36	R8	993	In cloud several times for this set of filters. Pump off while in cloud. Height varying between 8200' and 8400'
Filter run 6	P3	empty	empty	Bottom	14:12:44	14:23:36	R8	1222	
Filter run 7	P6	empty	empty	Top	14:34:08	14:58:00	R9	80	FL100. Flow seems very low

ARIES flight log

Flight: B204

Location: BESA

page 1 of

Date: 2/6/06

Operator(s): JAMES BOWLES

Resolution:

Gain A:

B:

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
		B204I							CHI	
12:13:05		204 J							NI	DUNDAV
		204 L							NI	RUN FOR SITE EARLY STAS
		204 M							NI	RUBBISH - TRIED TO CANCEL
12:27:02		204 N							CHI	
12:36:57		204 P							IR FAST	16 cm.
12:39:02		204 Q							CHI	2 cm
12:50:01		204 R							IR - FAST	16 cm.
12:51:53		204 S							CHI	2 cm.
13:00:37		204 T							IR - FAST	16 cm.
13:02:34		B204 U							CHI	2 cm
13:10:19		" V							IR - FAST	16 cm
13:16:08		" W							IR - FAST	16 cm
13:18:07		" X							CHI	2 cm.
13:29:29		" Y							CHI	2
13:43:13		" Z							CHI	2
13:45:03		" 00							NI	2
13:47:52		" 01							CHI	2
13:49:11		" 2							NI	2

IR FAST
DONE IN
HERE
SOMEWHAT

SWS and SHIMS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B204	Date	02/06/06	Operat or(s)	Ian Rule	log page	1	of	2
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Note to operator: Indicate whether entry refers to SWS or SHIMS

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	S W S	U S H	L S H
				Vis	NIR				

0839						Laptop time checked ok			
						Shims cleaned today, and a lot of dirt came off (not cleaned for B203)			
0900						All sws and shims modules now working			
100328		ground	shims	50	200	Shims running, clear skies, haze		x	
1014		ground	Various	50	200	Sws ok	x		
1114						Shims nir dropped out at 18 deg			
114450						Take off Beja			
115041						Start video, count = 0:00:00			
115236									
115736	P1	FL100	Nad - 6			Start profile, shims now ok			
1158			Nad - 6	100	200		x		
1158			shims	50	200			X	
1205			nad						
1212		50'				End profile			
121803	R1.1	500	Nad - 6	100	200	Start hal run over runway	x		
121833						End run			
122303	R1.2	500				Start hal run over grass			
122332						End run			
122834	R2.1	1000'	Nad - 6	100	200	Start run across runway			
						End run			
123652	R3.1	3000'	"	"	"	Start run across runway			
123735						End run			
124325	R4.1	5000'				Start run across runway			
124411						End run			
124945	R4.2	5000'	"	"	"	Start run across runway			
125020						End run			
125521			shims	30	200			x	
130004	R5.1	FL100	Nad - 6	100	200	Start run across runway	x		
130040						End run			
131003	R5.2	FL100	Nad - 6	100	200	Start run across runway	x		
131056						End run			
131536	R5.3	FL100	Nad - 6	100	200	Start run across runway			
131617						End run			
132756	P2	FL100	nad	100	200	Start profile			
133913		50'				End profile			
134451	R6.1	500'	nad			Start run along runway			
134524						End run			
134906	R6.2	500'	Nad - 6	100	200	Start run along grass			
134938						End run			
135433	R6.3	500				Start run along the grass			
135505						End run, end neon flying, start looking for cumulus			
140252			Zen +6	100	200	Looking for Cu, sws not really needed			
140621	P3	FL100	Zen +6	100	200				
1406			shims	30	200				
140824			Zen +6	50	200				
140909		FL70				End profile			
140936	P4					Start profile			

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B 204**.....

 Date **02/06/2006**.....

 Operator's name: **Wilson**.....

 Page **1** of **3**.....

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
11800	—	—	12.0			↗	+7	START PROGRAM before taxi. Pumping up to +42c
115519	positioning	FL100	11.5	2.8	67.4	↗	42	increasing to 45°C. V. dry air.
115734	P1	FL100 ↓		2.8	70.0	—	45	start P1
120258	P1	2800ft	14.5	32	75	—	45	interrupt P1 @ 2800ft
120842	P1	2500ft	12.4	32	77	—	45	re start P1 - bumps.
121236	P1	500ft	13.	34	78		45	end P1 @ 50ft
121630		500ft	13.3	37	74	↓	45	cycling temp down to +8c
121801	R1.1	500ft	13.4	36	62	↓	30	start R1.1 OVER Runway
121833	R1.1	—	—	37	59	↘	24	end R1.1
122301	R1.2	—	13.5	35	64	↘	19	start R1.2 side of Runway.
122332	R1.2	—	—	—	—	↓	18	end
122832	R2.1	1000ft	17.2	35	36	↘	13	start R2.1 across Runway (bumpy!)
122904	R2.1	1000ft	12.8	34	35	↘	12	end
123046	—	3000ft	12.3	28	35	↘	10	Pumping up to 45c.
123650	R3.1	3000	12.2	31.5	74	↗	44	start R3.1 @ 3000ft over Runway
123730	R3.1	3000ft	12.2	27	74	—	44	end R3.1
124324	R4.1	5000ft	11.4	22	78	—	44	start R4.1 offset of Beja Runway
124409	R4.1	5000ft	11.4	22	78	—	44	end R4.1
124943	R4.2	5000ft	12	22	78	—	44	start R4.2
125018	R4.2	—	12	22	78	—	44	end R4.2

Wet Nephelometer Log

 Flight No **B.204**

 Date **02/06/06**

 Operator's name: **Wilson**

 Page **2** of **3**

GMT	Run	Height	Sample flow	Dry neph RH	Wet neph RH	Temp ramp	T _{water}	Remarks
130003	R5.1	R100	12.2	0	76	-	45	start R5.1
130034	5.1	100	12.2	0	76	-	45	end R5.1
131002	5.2	100	12.2	2.2	77	-	45	start R5.2
131055	5.2	100	12.2	2.2	78	-	45	end R5.2
131534	R5.3	100	12.3	4.4	78	-	45	start R5.3
131616	5.3	100	12.4	5.0	78	-	45	end R5.3
132755	P2	R400	12.4	5.8	78	-	45	start P2
133910	P2	50ft	14.1	37	87		45	end P2
134200		50ft	14.0	36.7	79	↘	45	cycling temp down towards +8°C.
134451	R6.1							
134522	R6.1							
134802		50ft	14.1	35	53	↘	20°C	
134906	R6.2	500ft	14.1	34	50	↘	18	LAMP !!
134938	R6.2	500ft	14.1	37	48	↘	15	
135209		500ft	14.1	38	45	→	13	now ramping up to 45°C.
135443	R6.3	500ft	14.1	37	64	→	38	Start. R6.3
135503	R6.3	500ft	14.1	37	73	→	44	end R6.3
135700								END NEW SORTIE !! Climbing to FL100.
141939	R6.4		12.1	19	75	↘	40	ramping down to +5°C

IR CAMERA FLIGHT LOG

Flight No. B204
 Date 2/6/06
 Fitted Lens 100mm
 Active NUC 050126NUC3
 BPM Filename DBTEST!

Campaign CAPEX/NEON
 Operator JOSS
 Camera Angle -35°

Source Ref. Temp.	Hot	<u>5</u>
	Cold	<u>40</u>

DATA RECORDING		Run	Height	Remarks
Start Time	Stop Time	Number		
101224	31			PREFLIGHT CAL
101324	35			
101424	38			
101524	41			
101624	43			
101724	45			
101824	47			
101924	49			
102024	51			
102124	54			
102224	56			
102324	57			
102424	59			
102524	61			
115400	115547	Transit	10000'	
121903	121937	500'		Runway run
122314	122335	500'		Runway viewed
122645	122907	1000'		Good view for IR - ARIES module
122650	122724	3000'		Good run
125024	124606	5000'		Not in view, displaced too much
124943	125024	5000'		Good crossing:-
125949	130126	10000'		Runway @ end of run.
131003	131054	10000'		Good Runway view
131536	131643	10000'		Runway view @ end
13	134523	500'		Airport grass
134907	134943	500'		Runway view
1354	135507	500'		Runway view + grass
150924	46°C			
151024	48			
151124	50.5	(51)		
151224	53			
151324	55			
151424	57			
151524	59			
151624	61			
151724	62			

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B 204** Date: 2nd June 2006

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	Y
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	Y
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	N
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	N	Racks:	
FWVS	N	INC	N
<u>Radiometers</u>		CCN / CPC	Y
Upper Clear	Y	CVI	Y
“ Red	Y		
“ Silicon	Y		
“ SHIMS	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	Y
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	Y
		AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
IR Camera	Y		
TAFTS	N	<u>Others:</u>	
MARSS	Y	AVAPS	N
DEIMOS	N	IR Camera	Y
ARIES	Y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	N	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	N
CO	Y	CPI	N
ORAC	N	Noxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B204

Date: 2nd June 2006

Instruments

1. Upper BBRs and SHIMS cleaned pre-flight. All instruments had high levels of dirt adhered to them. The upper BBRs could not be cleaned for yesterday's flight B203 as a suitable method of access could not be found.
2. SATCOM-C reports "system clock error in CMOS clock." Turn-around message received in pre-flight check.
3. CVI failed during flight, but recovered.

Aircraft

Satcom Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B204:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting completion of post flight processing
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
IR Camera Processing log	IR Camera Processing log not currently available

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

1 x IR / Forward Facing Cameras

2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

Dave Kindred

EU Aircraft Liaison Officer
Observations Based Research
Jupiter Wing J-M-W014
Met Office
FitzRoy Road
Exeter
Ex1 3PB
UK

Tel: +44 (0)1392 88 4285

Fax: +44 (0)1392 88 5681

E-mail: dave.kindred@metoffice.gov.uk